

A Study of the Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycines with Some Metal Ions: Part XVII. Rotatometry of N-N'-Dibzenesulphonyl-L-Cystine

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The stepwise acid dissociation of the optically active ligand N-N'-dibzenesulphonyl-L-cystine (DBSC, RH_4 or $RSSR$) and its complex formation with Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) ions have been followed "Rotatometrically" in (1:1) aqueous-dioxan at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.50$) at $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. The successive acid dissociation constants (k_2^* and k_1^*) of the ligand DBSC and formation constant of its Cu(II) chelate $Cu(RH_2)$ have been determined and the values of pk_2^* , pk_1^* and $\log K$ are found to be 4.04 ± 0.04 , 4.68 ± 0.04 and 3.29 ± 0.04 respectively. The results are in good agreement with those obtained potentiometrically under identical conditions. The formation constants of Zn(II) and Cd(II) chelates of DBSC could not be evaluated due to the commencement of precipitation at the early stages of complex formation. Molar rotation $[M]_D^{30}$ values of various active species such as RH_4 , RH_3^- , RH_2^{2-} and $Cu(RH_2)$ have been evaluated and are found to be -445.1 , -655.2 , -811.2 and $+241.3$ degree mole $^{-1}$ under the experimental conditions.

An excellent study of the effect of added alkali on the optical activity of aminoacids has been made by Wood¹. More recently Ghosh and co-workers^{2,3} have studied the effect of variation of pH and the presence of metal ions [Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II)] on the optical activity of the ligand N-benzenesulphonyl-L-glutamic acid. It has been well established that optical rotations of optically active ligands suffer change during the course of their neutralisation and as well as complex formation with metal ions. Sometimes sign of rotation is reversed. A plot of observed optical rotation maintaining the total concentration of the optically active ligand constant throughout as a function of pH has been termed as *Rotatometric Titration*⁴. The plots are useful in determining the pH range at which various optically active species exist. The change in optical rotation during the course of a reaction has been ascribed to be due to the appearance of some new active species in the solution as well as to the disappearance of the original active species. When the active ligand is a weak acid or a weak base, its complex formations with metal ions or its ionisation are accompanied by changes in pH, as a result, optical rotation values are changed with change of pH of the solution containing the active ligand. If the reaction occurs in stages and the species formed possess markedly different optical rotations, distinct breaks or inflections may be obtained if the reaction is followed rotatometrically. Rotation maxima or minima in the rotatometric titration curves indicate the rotation due to the newly formed species. The position of such maxima

or minima indicates the pH of maximum formation of that species as well as the pH range in which it exists. Constancy of optical rotation with variation of pH indicates the presence of the same active species in this pH range. Thus the end points of rotatometric titrations can easily be detected.

In the present investigation the stepwise acid dissociation and complex formation with Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) ions of the optically active ligand N-N'-dibzenesulphonyl-L-cystine (DBSC, RH_4 or $RSSR$) (I) have been followed rotatometrically and its successive acid dissociation constants (k_2^* and k_1^*), formation constant (K) of its Cu(II) chelate

$Cu(RH_2)$ and the molar rotation $[M]_D^{30}$ values of the species RH_4 , RH_3^- , RH_2^{2-} and $Cu(RH_2)$ have been determined in (1:1) aqueous-dioxan at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.50$). Reactions of Zn(II) and Cd(II) ions with DBSC could not be followed rotatometrically due to the commencement of precipitation of oxides at the very early stages of complex formation.

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Experimental

Method :

For the determination of successive acid dissociation constants of the ligand, optical rotation of a number of solutions of the ligand each containing the same amount of the ligand, maintained at different pH values at a constant ionic strength were measured and plotted against pH. For the determination of formation constants of metal chelates, optical rotation of a number of solutions containing definite amount of the metal ion and the ligand adjusted to different pH values at a constant ionic strength were measured and plotted against pH of the solution as well as against the negative logarithm of free ligand concentration as may be necessary. The molar rotation $[M]_D$ values of various species were also evaluated from the data or by graphical extrapolation from the inflections of such plots and were refined by successive approximation.

Materials :

The ligand DBSC was prepared and purified by following the usual procedure^{5,6}. All other reagents were either of A.R. quality or properly purified and their solutions were made in double distilled CO₂-free water and purified dioxan⁷.

Ligand solutions : A 250 ml of 0.1069M solution of DBSC was prepared in purified dioxan. For the determination of dissociation constants of the ligand, 4.50 ml of the ligand solution together with 8.0 ml of purified dioxan were placed in a number of 25 ml measuring flasks, increasing amount of NaOH solution, requisite amounts of NaClO₄ solution and water were added to each flask so as to get solutions at different pH values at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.50$). The solutions were each $19.23 \times 10^{-3}M$ with respect to DBSC in (1 : 1) aqueous-dioxan.

Metal-ligand solutions : For the determination of formation constants of metal chelates, in addition to 4.50 ml of DBSC solution and 8.0 ml of purified dioxan, an amount of M²⁺ (M = Cu, Zn and Cd) ion solution were placed in each flask so that metal : ligand ratio becomes 1 : 1; increasing amounts of NaOH solution, requisite amounts of NaClO₄ solution and water were added as before.

The flasks were shaken well and were allowed to attain equilibrium at the required temperature. Contractions in volume were made up with (1 : 1) aqueous-dioxan maintained at this temperature.

Apparatus :

Measurements of pH values of the solutions were made with the help of a Cambridge Portable Type pH-Meter. Optical rotations due to sodium light were recorded with the help of a photoelectric polarimeter using a 0.25 dm tube. Data are stated in Tables 1 and 3. The observed rotations were plotted against pH (Fig. 1).

Results and Discussion

Acid dissociation constants (k_2^* and k_1^*) of DBSC :

Optical rotation of DBSC (RH₄) has showed a decrease with increase of pH of the solution (Fig. 1)

up to pH ≈ 6.50 , after which, rotation remained constant on further increase of pH of the solution.

Fig. 1. Rotatometric titration curve of DBSC.

Experimental points : DBSC; \odot DBSC+Cu(II); Δ DBSC+Zn(II); \square DBSC+Cd(II); Calculated curve using rotatometric $pk_2^* = 4.04$, $pk_1^* = 4.68$. — — —

This constancy of rotation with increase of pH indicates the end point of the rotatometric titration. The fall in rotation with increase of pH of DBSC solution is due to the appearance of some new species in the solution, which may be RH₃⁻ and RH₂²⁻ ions as a result of stepwise acid dissociation of RH₄ as represented by the reactions (1) and (2)

for which the successive acid dissociation constants are given by equations (3) and (4)

$$k_2^* = \frac{[RH_3^-][H^+]}{[RH_4]} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$k_1^* = \frac{[RH_2^{2-}][H^+]}{[RH_3^-]} \quad \dots (4)$$

Optical rotation is an additive property. Optical rotation of a solution is the algebraic sum of rotations due to all the active species present in it. Thus at any stage of the titration of DBSC after attainment of equilibrium the observed rotation α is given by

$$\alpha = \frac{R_4}{40} [Mr_4]_D + \frac{R_3}{40} [Mr_3]_D + \frac{R_2}{40} [Mr_2]_D \quad \dots (5)$$

where $[M_{r_4}]_D$, $[M_{r_3}]_D$ and $[M_{r_2}]_D$ are the molar rotations of the species RH_4 , RH_3^- and RH_2^{2-} respectively and R_4 , R_3 and R_2 are their equilibrium concentrations.

The molar rotation $[M]_D$ values have been calculated from the relation⁸

$$[M]_D = \frac{10\alpha}{l m} \quad \dots (6)$$

where α is the observed optical rotation of m molar solution of the optically active species in a 1 dm tube. Thus for a 0.25 dm tube

$$\alpha = \frac{m}{40} [M]_D \quad \dots (7)$$

Thus if a , b and c be the observed optical rotations of R molar solutions of RH_4 , RH_3^- and RH_2^{2-} respectively, where R is the total concentration of the ligand DBSC, one may get from equations (5) and (7)

$$\alpha = \frac{aR_4 + bR_3 + cR_2}{R_4 + R_3 + R_2} \quad \dots (8)$$

where

$$R = R_4 + R_3 + R_2 \quad \dots (9)$$

From the plot (Fig. 1) of $\alpha_{(obs.)}$ against pH , the value of c can easily be extrapolated, but those of a and b could not be accurately determined—evidently due to mutual overlapping of steps (1) and (2). Now from equations (3), (4) and (9) one may obtain

$$R_2 = \frac{R}{\frac{[H^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} + \frac{[H^+]}{k_1^*} + 1} \quad \dots (10)$$

and from (3), (4), (8) and (9)

$$\left(\frac{\alpha R}{R_2} - c \right) \cdot \frac{1}{[H^+]} = a \cdot \frac{[H^+]}{k_1^* k_2^*} + \frac{b}{k_1^*} \quad \dots (11)$$

With the help of linear plot of

$$\left(\frac{\alpha R}{R_2} - c \right) \cdot \frac{1}{[H^+]} \text{ against } \frac{[H^+]}{k_1^* k_2^*}$$

the values of a and b have been obtained from the slope and intercept of the straight line taking the values of practical dissociation constants⁹ (k_2^* and k_1^*) as obtained potentiometrically¹⁰ under identical conditions, and also considering the latter stages of the titration, when R_4 is negligibly small, one may get from (11)

$$\log \left(\frac{\alpha R}{R_2} - c \right) = (pk_1^* - pH) + \log b \quad \dots (12)$$

and the value of b has also been found out from the intercept of the linear plot of $\log \left(\frac{\alpha R}{R_2} - c \right)$ against $(pk_1^* - pH)$ using equation (12).

With the values of a , b and c at hand one may now re-evaluate k_2^* and k_1^* from the linear plot (Fig. 2) of the relation

$$\left(\frac{c - \alpha}{\alpha - a} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{[H^+]^2} = \frac{1}{k_1^*} \cdot \frac{\alpha - b}{\alpha - a} \cdot \frac{1}{[H^+]} + \frac{1}{k_1^* k_2^*} \quad \dots (13)$$

which may be deduced from equations (3), (4), (8) and (9). The values of a , b , k_2^* and k_1^* have been refined by successive approximation. Results are stated in Table 2.

Limits of error have been evaluated by comparing the experimental plot of $\alpha_{(obs.)}$ against pH with a calculated one obtained on plotting $\alpha_{(calc.)}$ against pH . The $\alpha_{(calc.)}$ values have been obtained from the relation

$$\alpha_{(calc.)} = \frac{a \cdot \frac{[H^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} + b \cdot \frac{[H^+]}{k_1^*} + c}{\frac{[H^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} + \frac{[H^+]}{k_1^*} + 1} \quad \dots (14)$$

employing the refined values of a , b , k_2^* , k_1^* and experimental value of c . Standard deviation (σ) have been calculated from the relation

$$\sigma = \pm \left[\frac{\sum (\alpha_{(obs.)} - \alpha_{(calc.)})^2}{\text{Number of observations}} \right]^{1/2} \quad \dots (15)$$

and are stated in Table 1. Molar rotation $[M]_D^{30}$ values of the species RH_4 , RH_3^- and RH_2^{2-} have been calculated employing equation (7) using the refined values of a , b and experimental value of c . Results are stated in Table 2.

Formation constant (K) of the complex $Cu(RH_2)$:

A sharp rise in the optical rotation with increase of pH has been observed in the rotatometric titration of DBSC in presence of Cu^{2+} ions (Fig. 1). Evidently DBSC undergoes complex formation with Cu^{2+} ions with the formation of the active species $Cu(RH_2)$ according to the reaction (16).

which occurs together with the stepwise acid dissociation (1) and (2) of DBSC with increase of pH of the solution. The formation constant (K) of the complex $Cu(RH_2)$ is given by equation (17)

$$K = \frac{[Cu(RH_2)]}{[Cu^{2+}][RH_4]} \quad \dots (17)$$

Now the concentrations of the species $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})^-$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{R})^{2-}$ which may arise as a result of stepwise acid dissociation¹⁰ of $\text{Cu}(\text{RH}_2)$ are assumed negligible at the early stages of complex formation, then after attainment of equilibrium the following relations will hold good

$$R = R_4 + R_3 + R_2 + M_1 \quad \dots (18)$$

$$M = M_0 + M_1 \quad \dots (19)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{aR_4 + bR_3 + cR_2 + dM_1}{R_4 + R_3 + R_2 + M_1} \quad \dots (20)$$

where M is the initial concentration of Cu^{2+} ion, M_0 and M_1 are the equilibrium concentrations of free Cu^{2+} ion and the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{RH}_2)$ respectively, d is the observed optical rotation of a R molar solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{RH}_2)$ under the experimental conditions. The other notations have their usual meanings.

Molar rotation of the species $\text{Cu}(\text{RH}_2)$ has been obtained from the relation

$$[M]_D = \frac{40.d}{R} \quad \dots (21)$$

The value of K may be obtained from the intercept of the linear plot of R_2 against

$$\frac{M(d-\alpha)}{B}$$

using the relation

$$\frac{M(d-\alpha)}{B} = R_2 + \frac{1}{K} \quad \dots (22)$$

where

$$B = \left[(\alpha - a) \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} + (\alpha - b) \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1^*} + (\alpha - c) \right];$$

and the value of R_2 from the relation

$$R_2 = \frac{R(d-\alpha)}{(d-a) \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} + (d-b) \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1^*} + (d-c)} \quad \dots (23)$$

One may deduce the relations (22) and (23) from equations (3), (4), (17), (18), (19) and (20). But as the value of d could not be obtained from the rotatometric titration curve (Fig. 1), it is not possible to find out R_2 from equation (23) and hence K from the graphical solution of equation (22).

An approximate value of R_2 have been obtained employing the potentiometrically determined¹⁰ value of K as follows. On solving equations (3), (4), (17), (18) and (19) one may obtain

$$R = R_2 \left(\frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1^*} + 1 \right) + \frac{MKR_2}{1 + KR_2} \quad \dots (24)$$

which may be arranged in a quadratic equation in R_2 , such that

Fig. 2. Linear plot for k_2^* and k_1^* of DBSC.

$$R_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[- \left(\frac{A - K(R - M)}{AK} \right) \pm \left\{ \left(\frac{A - K(R - M)}{AK} \right)^2 + \frac{4R}{AK} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad \dots (25)$$

where

$$A = \left[\frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1^*} + 1 \right].$$

R_2 values have been obtained from equation (25) using the rotatometric values of k_2^* and k_1^* and potentiometric value of K . The value of d has

Fig. 3. Evaluation of d for $\text{Cu}(\text{RH}_2)$.

TABLE 1

ROTATOMETRIC TITRATION OF DBSC (RH₄) AT 30° ± 0.5°. DBSC = 19.23 × 10⁻³M (1:1) AQUEOUS DIOXAN; μ = 0.50. POTENTIOMETRIC p*k*₂^{*}, 4.02; p*k*₁^{*}, 4.70 AND 'c', -0.390°,

pH	α _(obs.) degree	α _(calc.) degree using rotatometric p <i>k</i> ₂ [*] = 4.04 p <i>k</i> ₁ [*] = 4.68]	pH	α _(obs.) degree	α _(calc.) degree using rotatometric p <i>k</i> ₂ [*] = 4.04 p <i>k</i> ₁ [*] = 4.68
2.05	-0.215	-0.215	5.08	-0.365	-0.365
2.51	-0.215	-0.217	5.38	-0.375	-0.376
2.90	-0.220	-0.221	5.56	-0.380	-0.380
3.20	-0.225	-0.226	5.88	-0.385	-0.386
3.61	-0.245	-0.244	6.48	-0.390	-0.388
3.83	-0.260	-0.260	7.25	-0.390	-0.389
4.13	-0.285	-0.286	8.05	-0.390	-0.390
4.39	-0.310	-0.314	9.25	-0.390	-0.390
4.60	-0.330	-0.331	9.75	-0.390	-0.390
4.88	-0.350	-0.353	10.50	-0.390	-0.390

Standard deviation (σ) = ±0.002

TABLE 2

RESULTS OF ROTATOMETRIC TITRATION OF DBSC (RH₄).DBSC = 19.23 × 10⁻³M.

Species	RH ₄ 'a' (degree)	RH ₃ ⁻ 'b' (degree)	RH ₂ ²⁻ 'c' (degree)	p <i>k</i> ₂ [*]	p <i>k</i> ₁ [*]
Optical rotation in a 0.25 dm tube	(i) From eqn. (11) -0.214 (ii) Refined -0.214	(i) From eqn. (11) -0.315 (ii) From eqn. (12) -0.316 (iii) Refined -0.315	From graphical extrapolation -0.390	4.04 ± 0.04 (Potentiometric values) (4.02 ± 0.02)	4.68 ± 0.04 (4.70 ± 0.02)
Molar rotation [M] _D ³⁰ ± 0.05 deg. mole ⁻¹	-445.1	-655.2	-811.2		

TABLE 3

ROTATOMETRIC TITRATION OF DBSC(RH₄) IN PRESENCE OF Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ AND Cd²⁺ IONS AT 30° ± 0.5°
DBSC = 19.23 × 10⁻³M; M²⁺(M = Cu, Zn, Cd) = 19.23 × 10⁻³ IN (1:1) AQUEOUS DIOXAN;
μ = 0.50, 'a' -0.214°; 'b', -0.315°; 'c' -0.390°. ROTATOMETRIC p*k*₂^{*}, 4.04; p*k*₁^{*}, 4.68. FOR Cu(RH₂), POTENTIO-
METRIC log K, 3.30

pH	α _(obs.) degree	R ₂ × 10 ⁵ (refined)	α _(calc.) degree using rotatometric p <i>k</i> ₂ [*] = 4.04, p <i>k</i> ₁ [*] = 4.68, log K = 3.29	DBSC + Zn(II)		DBSC + Cd(II)	
				pH	α _(obs.) degree	pH	α _(obs.) degree
2.10	-0.215	0.06	-0.215	2.95	-0.220	2.85	-0.220
2.64	-0.215	0.67	-0.212	3.06	-0.225	3.32	-0.230
3.04	-0.200	3.72	-0.201	3.28	-0.230	3.60	-0.240
3.21	-0.185	7.31	-0.185	3.60	-0.245	3.72	-0.250
3.38	-0.160	13.52	-0.162	3.80	-0.265	3.96	-0.270
3.54	-0.130	22.60	-0.126	4.04	-0.285	4.28	-0.300
3.73	-0.095	39.21	-0.094	4.32	-0.305	4.48	-0.320
3.86	-0.060	50.88	-0.064	4.48	-0.320	4.72	-0.340
3.95	+0.050	4.76	-0.345	5.00	-0.360
4.11	+0.115	4.84	-0.350	5.16	-0.370
4.33	+0.205	5.20	-0.355	5.76	-0.375
...	5.40	-0.335	6.18	-0.355
...	6.04	-0.270	6.80	-0.315

Standard deviation (σ) = ±0.0024

been evaluated from the intercept of the linear plot (Fig. 3) of $\alpha_{(obs.)}$ against $B(1+KR_2)/MK$ using the relation

$$\alpha = - \frac{B(1+KR_2)}{KM} + d \quad \dots (26)$$

which may be obtained from equation (22). The refined values of R_2 have now been obtained from equation (23) using rotatometric values of k_2^* , k_1^* and the value of d evaluated from graphical solution of equation (26). The values of d and R_2 have been refined by successive approximation. Finally the value of K has been obtained from the intercept of the plot (Fig. 4) of $(d-\alpha)M/B$ against R_2 (refined), using equation (22), and subsequently

Fig. 4. Linear plot for K of $\text{Cu}(\text{RH}_2)$.

refined by successive approximation. The refined value of $\log K$ has been shown in Table 4 which also contains the molar rotation $[M]_D^{30}$ of the species $\text{Cu}(\text{RH}_2)$ obtained from equation (21) using refined value of d .

TABLE 4—RESULTS OF ROTATOMETRIC TITRATION OF DBSC IN PRESENCE OF Cu^{2+} IONS
DBSC = $19.23 \times 10^{-3} M$; Cu^{2+} = $19.23 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Species	$\text{Cu}(\text{RH}_2)$
Optical rotation in a 0.25 dm tube (degree)	+0.116 (refined)
Molar rotation $[M]_D^{30} \pm 0.5$ degree mole ⁻¹	+214.3
Rotatometric $\log K$ (refined)	3.29 ± 0.04
Potentiometric $\log K$ (refined)	3.30 ± 0.02

The standard deviation (σ) has also been calculated employing the equation (15), for which the $\alpha_{(calc.)}$ values have been obtained from the equation

$$\alpha_{(calc.)} = \frac{R_2}{R} \left[a. \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1^* k_2^*} + b. \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1^*} + c + d. \frac{MK}{1+KR_2} \right] \quad \dots (27)$$

which may be deduced from equations (3), (4), (17), (18), (19) and (20). Data and results are stated in Table 3.

The rotatometric titration of DBSC in presence of $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ could not be completed due to intense blue colouration of the solution at higher pH values.

Reactions of DBSC with $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$:

Rotatometric titration of DBSC in presence of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ions indicate no complex formation at lower pH values, as the rotatometric titration curve (Fig. 1) for these titrations follow the same path as the curve obtained in the absence of these ions. This indicates that Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ions have no influence on the optical activity of the ligand DBSC, in other words there is no complex formation between the ligand and these metal ions at these pH values. At comparatively higher pH values of the solution optical rotation of DBSC has showed an increase due to the presence of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ions—indicating complex formation. But the titrations could not be completed due to the commencement of precipitation of oxides at higher pH values of the solutions.

From the nature of the rotatometric titration curves (Fig. 1) it is apparent that the stability of DBSC chelates are in the order $\text{Cu}(\text{II}) \gg \text{Zn}(\text{II}) > \text{Cd}(\text{II})$. Similar order of stabilities has also been obtained from potentiometric study¹⁰. The order may be correlated to the gradual decreases of electronegativity¹¹ in the sequence Cu-Zn-Cd .

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